

Ethics Panel Report

2018 Data Science Leadership Summit

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Executive Summary

During the 2018 Data Science Leadership Summit, a panel discussion on data ethics generated active participation. The panel featured opening remarks by the chairs and presentations by three panelists representing a broad, multidisciplinary range of views—computer science, history and philosophy of science, and developmental psychology—followed by a question-and-answer period that included lively audience participation. Key topics covered in the panel included an overview of pedagogical approaches to engaging students with human and societal issues in data science, the historical context of ethics and science from the perspective of human-subjects research ethics, and a comparison between approaches to ethical research in industry and academia and the limits of Institutional Review Boards in predicting ethical harms created by technology. Some of the main takeaways from the ethics panel and the discussion that followed were: group consensus is that ethics education is a critical component of data science education; current protections (e.g., protections to maintain privacy, limit the targeting of vulnerable populations, minimize bias) are currently inadequate and must be updated in response to evolving world of technology; differing views and some uncertainty persist over how to adequately approach ethics education in data science; conversations about ethics must move beyond a discussion of individual actions within the data science workflow to include the larger social context and societal structures, as well as to broaden participation and justice.

Recommendations

- 1. Ethics needs to be a component of every data science education program. This can take the form of modules that can be easily infused into existing classes, and also an entire course that can be part of a data science curriculum. However, the model of ethics education will need to be adapted to each program.**
- 2. A national community of practice and shared resources for ethics in data science education should be formed.**
- 3. Ethics should be considered through every step of the data life cycle, and practices and tools should be developed to support this work and not just be addressed as part of a requirements checklist in data science projects.**
- 4. Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) and insights about ethics from other disciplines represent an important starting point, but they alone are not equipped to handle new potential harms stemming from technological advances.**
- 5. Ethics for data science needs to be understood as requiring new foundational thinking about technology, society, and human beings, and a broad conception that engages issues of human values, broad participation, and justice.**
- 6. Opportunities to reflect on ethics should be provided at different stages of data science practitioners' careers.**

7. The national data science leadership community must actively recruit experts in ethics to define appropriate strategies.

Opening Remarks

The Data Science Leadership Summit had a panel on ethics, chaired by Drs. Stan Ahalt and Jay Aikat, from the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (UNC-Chapel Hill). The panel included three panelists: Dr. Cathryn Carson, Dr. Lucy Erickson, and Dr. Jeannette Wing. Prior to panelist presentations, Dr. Ahalt gave opening remarks, which provided a brief overview of ethics-related data science activities at UNC-Chapel Hill. He spoke about his experience in healthcare and biomedical informatics, including work on the NCATS Biomedical Data Translator and NIH Data Commons. Dr. Ahalt then noted that at the Renaissance Computing Institute (RENCI) at UNC-Chapel Hill, and in the Research Triangle area, there is an emphasis on the ethical issues for NIH-funded projects, often biomedical in nature. RENCi is in the process of creating a training course in data science geared towards US federal judges, as well as contributing to a data science curriculum for UNC. After Dr. Ahalt's remarks, the panelists gave brief presentations prior to a discussion with summit attendees, moderated by Dr. Ahalt and Dr. Aikat, and assisted by Ms. Sarah Davis.

Panelist Presentations

Dr. Cathryn Carson

Dr. Cathryn Carson, the faculty lead of the Data Science Undergraduate Program at the University of California, Berkeley, began with a 15-minute presentation entitled "Embedding Reflection on Human Contexts and Ethics". She began by addressing her academic background as a historian of science, and then spoke about a data ethics course she teaches called Human Contexts and Ethics of Data. As Dr. Carson explained, her engagement with ethics comes from her training in the history of twentieth-century physics and her time embedded among scientists, engineers and technologists in Berkeley's nuclear engineering department at the time of Fukushima. She pointed out that our definition and understanding of ethics in the context of data and technology is still being defined, and that the data science community itself is uncertain what it means by the term ethics. In her course (co-taught with Dr. Margo Boenig-Liptsin) she explores this open terrain, which lacks established principles and practices, with her students. She aims to prepare her students for a "data-fied" world in which ethical challenges are ubiquitous and entangled with data. She suggested that what many people mean by the term *ethics* pertains to the idea of creating and maintaining human good and social order, and suggested a working definition attributed to Paul Ricoeur, *Oneself as Another*: ethics is aiming at the "good life" with and for others, in just institutions. [LE1]

Dr. Carson explained that, at the ground level, data science research involves many practices and choices that have ethical ramifications, for example in the context of human dignity, privacy, and other harms. As data science becomes part of socio-technical systems, new levels of ethical thinking are needed, such as at the point at which decisions are made on the basis of predictive modeling (e.g., policing decisions are made on the basis of an algorithm). [LE2] Dr. Carson spoke about the ethical importance of a data science community that holds space for individuals with different life experiences (for instance, of exposure to bias) to

participate in sharing experiences and shaping values across the country, and at all levels; and about embedding attention and concern for these issues within social structures and social contexts. A key takeaway from her presentation was that despite misconceptions, ethical data science requires much more than individuals simply not being evil—which would have been unlikely to have averted the Cambridge Analytica scandal. Like all other sciences and technologies, such as nuclear physics, data science research is rife with potentially well-intentioned but nonetheless open-ended uses or harmful missteps. The same techniques and tools can be used for unjustified surveillance and for social good, and navigating this fundamental duality is not always easy. We must go beyond awareness of the evil of individuals, Dr. Carson argued, and instead develop an understanding of the social embedding aspects of ethics, to craft appropriate solutions to ethical problems.

Dr. Carson provided an overview of the Berkeley course, Human Contexts and Ethics of Data, which satisfies the corresponding requirement for Berkeley's Data Science major and minor. This course was drawn up by faculty with field-specific expertise, and is characterized by commitment to broadening the notion of ethics beyond that of the individual. Course enrollments consist of data science majors and minors as well as other interested students, enrolling around 200-300 in recent semesters. Enrollments are rising, as the popularity of data science continues to grow on campus, raising questions about scalability as projected number of students going through these courses reaches 1500/year. The main operating principle of the course is to assume that students have ethical intuitions and use those as a starting point from which to explore implicit norms and beliefs about ethical thinking and behavior. In the course, students engage in weekly reading assignments, reflections, vignettes, and group discussions, and learn about Codes of Practice, and Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) for ethical conduct of research. There is a final exam, but the emphasis is on the discussions and weekly grappling with difficult ethical questions, which go beyond the notion of individual ethical practices. [LE4]

Dr. Lucy Erickson

The second panelist, Dr. Lucy Erickson, a current AAAS Science and Technology Policy (S&TP) Fellow at the National Science Foundation, began with an explanation of how she became interested in the topics of data science ethics. Like other panelists, Dr. Erickson did not develop this interest through formal training, but rather through her experiences as a developmental psychologist embedded in the Computer and Information Sciences and Engineering (CISE) Directorate of the National Science Foundation (NSF) through the AAAS Science and Technology Policy Fellowship. She spoke about her experiences conducting human subjects research and the requisite ethical training completed by researchers working with human subjects, after sharing some observations about ethical considerations of the impact of technological developments on children. She began by contrasting the strict (but somewhat outdated) data privacy practices observed by infant and child academic researchers with the behavior of parents, who frequently share images of their children freely on social media with few reservations. She also noted the proliferation of “educational” apps directed at toddlers that are available for download. These purportedly “educational” apps frequently ignore knowledge of best practices for learning, such as the fact that distracting sound and visual effects peripheral to the learning task itself often detract from infant and children's learning.

Dr. Erickson then provided an overview of how the human-subjects ethical approval process grew out of flagrant violations of human rights, such as the Tuskegee syphilis experiment. Such high-profile violations led to the release of the Belmont Report in 1979 and

the passing of the Common Rule in 1981, which led to the creation of IRBs to oversee research with human subjects. The Belmont Report sets forth three main principles: respect for person, beneficence, and justice. Respect for person pertains to the need for participants to give informed, free, and voluntary consent that is not coercive. Coercion is a particular concern for any vulnerable population that cannot give true consent, such as prisoners and young children. Beneficence is concerned with doing good and avoiding harm. Finally, the principle of justice is concerned with the equal distributions of the risks and benefits—ensuring that one group does not disproportionately bear the risks of research with the potential to benefit a larger population.

Dr. Erickson noted that human-subjects researchers have extensive experience with ethical training and research practices, particularly in the context of data protection and privacy. In some ways, this may be viewed as a gold standard for data science research to emulate; however, there are real limitations in this training, as the human-subjects world is not prepared for the new technological developments that create new threats. For example, current standards focus on removing key fields of personally-identifiable information (PII). After PII removal, there may be few if any restrictions on what can be done with these data, which represents a concern as new techniques are developed to allow re-identification of data thought to be adequately de-identified. In addition, the landscape of ethical data science is much broader than issues of data sharing, although privacy is an important issue and one that has been receiving recent media attention. For example, algorithmic bias represents a major threat that is foreign to the human-subjects model of ethical research. Dr. Erickson argued that it is necessary to convene individuals representing a broad range of expertise to develop new standards for what is ethical and appropriate in the evolving research landscape. For example, informed consent tends to be viewed as a gold standard for research, but new questions are emerging about the extent to which it is truly possible to be informed of potential—perhaps harmful—outcomes. This is concerning in cases when an individual may consent for his or herself, but may be even more problematic when a person's inadequately informed consent affects another individual. As an example, consider the potential impact of providing consent for your child when you yourself cannot predict the long-term ramifications, or the effect sequencing your own DNA may have on your close blood relatives. Dr. Erickson concluded by suggesting that it might be useful, as a starting point, to develop some of the same kinds of online training modules that human subjects research uses, such as the Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative (CITI Program), which uses text with embedded case studies and quizzes. She also mentioned the possibility of working with researchers who study learning and sequencing of instructional content. These researchers may be willing to help test the best ways to instill ethical thinking into data science students.

Dr. Jeannette Wing

The third panelist was Dr. Jeannette Wing, who is currently the Avaneessians Director of the Data Sciences Institute at Columbia University, where she is also a professor of computer science. Dr. Wing also brings experience from time spent at Carnegie Mellon University, Microsoft, and at the National Science Foundation. She began by mentioning a controversial paper on emotion manipulation on Facebook (Kramer et al., PNAS) and reminding the audience that the concept of IRBs to govern the ethical conduct of research is specific to the university setting and not present in industry. The negative reactions to the revelation that Facebook manipulated content experienced by users to influence their emotional states spurred Microsoft Research, where Dr. Wing worked at the time, to draw up their own IRB-type process. This

process included checklists and audits to ensure products and services have reviews for privacy and ethical issues prior to release. She suggested that companies should adopt such processes because it is in their best interest to do so; however, she cautioned that IRBs alone are not a panacea. Dr. Wing argued that there is always a risk-benefit analysis that needs to balance technology, policy, and business, and thus appropriate course of action may not always be clear.

Dr. Wing then spoke about the importance of training and prioritization of ethics, both in industry settings and at universities. She argued that there is a great need to correct the culture around ethics in the technology sector. She then provided an overview of some of the ethical training efforts happening at Columbia, which include activities such as professional development courses, a capstone course involving real-world data, and “Data for Good” lunch seminars. She indicated that all instructors are encouraged to highlight ethical issues when appropriate (e.g., to bring up algorithmic bias in the context of learning about machine learning algorithms). Her goal for Columbia is to adopt an educational model similar to domains such as law, medicine, journalism, and business. She concluded by referencing community efforts and other places to use a starting point—such as the Belmont Report, ethical codes and tenets developed by the ACM, Data for Democracy, and Partnership for AI—and argued that although none of these are perfect, they represent initial work on which we can expand and build.

Discussion

Following the panelist presentations, Dr. Ahalt and Dr. Aikat led a moderated discussion to delve deeper into these issues. The discussion engaged the audience as well as the panelists, and many had personal experiences to share. There was group consensus that it is critical for data scientists and data science students—in both the public and private sector—to be educated in ethics from the very beginning of instruction. This need applies to the entire spectrum of data scientists: data collectors, data stewards, data users and re-users. Some felt that ethics education is also important for non-data scientists, who might be impacted by choices made by data scientists. In terms of training, the group felt that “one size fits all” approaches would be less effective than more tailored approaches. Some of the types of training mentioned included but were not limited to: formal education, informal learning, instruction in classrooms, training with MOOCs or other online formats, training led by instructors, and learning from peers. It was pointed out that effective ethics education may require some pedagogical approaches that differ from those typically used in data science classes, for example debates or case studies.

Questions of accreditation and certification were raised, as well as whether data scientists should be expected to take an oath, such as the Hippocratic oath taken by medical professionals. Both regulation and social norms were considered as mechanisms for enforcement. There was considerable discussion of the importance of organizational contexts within which data scientists work. Out of this came questions about the balance between formalizable measures generating a sense of individual accountability, such as codes of ethics, and a robust appreciation of larger organizational structures, such as companies or governments, that may have a more ambiguous relation to ethical standards. Educators may need to ask themselves how to discuss such questions with their students, for instance, around career paths.

Some of the key issues that emerged from the discussion were that the ways in which errors or poor practices can cause harm may be quite subtle and opaque compared to other

fields (e.g., nuclear power, or civil engineering). For example, subtle ethical issues can arise in many data science applications based on how patterns are discovered and used, from car driving behavior and communication patterns from computer networking to data collection by smartphone apps. In addition, although any profession can have a small number of rogue individuals, the scale at which a data scientist can cause harm, whether intentionally or unintentionally, may be much larger than in some other fields due to the pervasiveness of not only the data but the pervasiveness of algorithms that quickly become used in all aspects of life. For example, an algorithm intended to be helpful but that is inherently biased may harm more individuals than a malevolent surgeon.

In addition to issues of the scale of these potential harms, an important consideration is all of the potential aspects of data collection, processing, and analysis—throughout the entire the data life cycle—where potential ethical issues may arise¹. Ethical concerns are present throughout this data life cycle, in which data undergo a knowledge discovery process. Ethical concerns begin immediately at the time of data collection and subsequent sampling (e.g., missing a key demographic group), at data cleaning (e.g., removing an outlier or smoothing away noise that may represent meaningful variance of a particular subgroup), through data storage (e.g., storing sensitive personal data that may not be adequately de-identified), during pattern discovery (e.g., failing to develop robust algorithms lacking algorithmic biases; failing to carefully consider thoughtful threshold choices to prevent influencing the discovery or elimination of patterns), and with evaluation of the discovered patterns (e.g., failing to evaluate implicit or explicit biases). In addition, the entire process should also be carefully evaluated holistically to prevent the compounding ethical issues along the various steps of the data life cycle.

Finally, it was suggested that if we are to successfully deal with these issues, we must bring a broader cross-section of individuals representing relevant expertise to these leadership events and into the conversations. In addition, discussions of ethical aspects in data studies should be part of the main conference program at the leading data science conferences, and not simply addressed in co-located workshops, which may not be part of the mainstream discussions. Such discussions taking place in the core of these conferences will spark a broader discussion on how ethics can truly be infused into the many new data science methods and advances, as a continuous process.

¹ Janeja, V. (April, 2019). Do No Harm: An Ethical Data Life Cycle: <https://www.aaaspolicyfellowships.org/blog/do-no-harm-ethical-data-life-cycle>